

Dynamic Hip Screw with Derotational Screw In Neck of Femur Fractures

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Abstract

Background: Fracture of the neck of the femur remains a challenging injury due to risks of non-union and avascular necrosis. In young and physiologically active patients, internal fixation is preferred to preserve the native femoral head. Dynamic Hip Screw (DHS) fixation provides controlled compression at the fracture site; however, rotational instability of the femoral head during and after fixation may adversely affect outcomes. Supplementation with a derotation screw has been advocated to enhance rotational stability.

Objectives: To evaluate the functional and radiological outcomes of fracture neck of femur treated with Dynamic Hip Screw fixation supplemented with a derotation screw and to assess associated complications.

Materials and Methods: This prospective study included patients with fracture neck of the femur managed with DHS and an additional derotation screw. Patients were followed up at regular intervals with clinical and radiological assessments. Fracture union, implant position, and complications such as non-union, avascular necrosis, and implant failure were documented. Functional outcome was assessed using a standard hip scoring system.

Results: In a total of 20 patients, fracture union is achieved in 19 patients (95%) of the patients, with a mean union time of 15 weeks. According to the Harris Hip Score, Functional outcome showed excellent to good results in 15 patients (75%) with a mean HHS of 86. Complications were observed in 10% of the patients, which included non-union in 1 patient (5%) and avascular necrosis in 1 patient (5%). Better functional and radiological outcomes were noted in Garden II & III fractures compared to Garden IV. DHS with a derotational screw provided improved rotational stability with no incidence of implant failure.

Conclusion: Dynamic Hip Screw fixation supplemented with a derotation screw is an effective and reliable method for managing selected fractures of the neck of femur. The technique provides enhanced rotational stability, satisfactory union rates, and favourable functional outcomes with minimal complications.

Keywords: Fracture neck of femur, Dynamic Hip Screw, Derotation screw, Internal fixation, Functional outcome.

INTRODUCTION

Fractures of the neck of femur remain a significant challenge due to their **high morbidity** and **risk of fixation failure**.

Complications like **avascular necrosis**, **collapse of the neck** and **sheer stress** pose a significant challenge in treating these fractures.

Dynamic Hip Screw (DHS) has long been a standard implant for stable fracture patterns, however rotational stability of the femoral head remains a concern.

The addition of a **derotational screw aims to improve rotational control and enhance the fracture stability.**

AIM

To evaluate the **functional and radiological outcomes of Dynamic Hip Screw fixation with derotational screw** in the treatment of **neck of femur fractures.**

OBJECTIVES:

1. To assess the **rate and time of fracture union** following DHS with derotational screw fixation
2. To evaluate the **functional outcomes** using **Harris Hip Score** at regular follow up intervals
3. To determine the **incidence of complications** such as non-union, avascular necrosis, and implant failure.

INCLUSION CRITERIA

- Adult patients (18 - 60 years)
- Post traumatic neck of femur fractures.
- Garden type II-IV / Pauwels type II-III fractures.

EXCLUSION CRITERIA

- Pathological fractures
- Old neglected or non union fractures
- Associated ipsilateral lower limb injuries

SURGICAL TECHNIQUE

- Patient in supine position on fracture table with traction and internal rotation.
- Closed reduction under C-arm (check AP and lateral views)
- Standard lateral approach to the proximal femur.
- Guidewire inserted for DHS lag screw placement through the inferomedial part of the femoral head.
- Guide wire passed superior and parallel to the first guide wire.
- DHS lag screw inserted over the inferomedial guidewire after reaming.
- Derotational screw (cannulated cancellous screw 6.5mm) placed superior and parallel to the DHS lag screw over the second guide wire.
- Both screws advanced 10mm short of the subchondral bone.
- Side plate applied and fixed with cortical screws to the femoral shaft.
- Final reduction and fixation checked under C-arm (AP and lateral).

POST OPERATIVE PROTOCOL

- Quadriceps and ankle exercises from post operative day 1
- Non weight bearing or partial weight bearing decided depending on fracture pattern for 6 weeks.
- Full weight bearing depending on radiological union after 6 weeks.

Results

In a total of 20 patients, fracture union is achieved in 19 patients (95%) of the patients, with a mean union time of 15 weeks

According to Harris Hip Score, Functional outcome showed excellent to good results in 15 patients (75%) of patients with a mean HHS of 86.

Complications were observed in 10% of the patients

- Non-union in 1 patients (5%).
- Avascular necrosis in 1 patient (5%).
- Better functional and radiological outcomes were noted in Garden II & III fractures compared to Garden IV.
- DHS with derotational screw provided improved rotational stability with no incidence of implant failure.

CASE 1

PRE OPERATIVE XRAY

POST OPERATIVE XRAY

6 WEEKS POST OP

12 WEEKS POST OP XRAY

24 WEEKS POST OP

CASE 2

PRE OPERATIVE XRA

POST OPERATIVE XRAY

6 WEEKS POST OP XRAY

12 WEEKS POST OP XRAY

24 WEEKS POST OP XRAY

CASE 3

PRE OPERATIVE XRAY

POST OPERATIVE XRAY

6 WEEKS POST OP XRAY

12 WEEKS POST OP XRAY

24 WEEKS POST OP XRAY

CASE 4

PRE OPERATIVE XRAY

POST OPERATIVE XRAY

6 WEEKS POST OP XRAY

12 WEEKS POST OP XRAY

24 WEEKS POST OP XRAY

DISCUSSION

Femoral neck fractures in young adults have high risk of **rotational instability, non-union, and AVN**.

DHS provides controlled **dynamic compression**, but **rotational control** is limited in vertical (Pauwels II/III) and displaced fractures.

Adding a **derotational screw** increased **rotational stability**, maintained reduction, and prevented varus collapse.

DHS + derotational screw is **simple, cost-effective**, and biomechanically stronger than DHS alone.

Most patients achieved **excellent-good outcomes** (Harris Hip Score improvement) with minimal complications.

CONCLUSION

- DHS with derotational screw provides a **stable and reliable construct**.
- Reduced rotational instability, maintains reduction, and **improves the biomechanical stability** of fixation.
- It achieves **good union rates and functional outcomes** in most patients.
- Useful especially in **vertical/displaced fractures** (Pauwels II–III, Garden III–IV).
- A simple modification to standard DHS that can reduce complications like **varus collapse** and **non-union**.

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